

Analysis of ground reaction forces by forearm crutches during instep kick in amputee football

Kobayashi, T^a, Urabe, Y^a, Fujishita, H^b, Sasadai, J^a, Maeda, N^a

^a Graduate School of Biomedical and Health Sciences, Hiroshima University, Hiroshima, Japan

^b Sports Medical Center, Hiroshima University Hospital, Hiroshima, Japan

* Corresponding author: Takumi Kobayashi; tkobayashi0617@hiroshima-u.ac.jp

Abstract The purpose of this study was to compare the difference in ground reaction forces (GRF) generated by forearm crutches during instep kick of amputee football players between experienced players and beginners. 12 collegiate students without amputation of their leg participated in this study as the subjects simulated amputee. They were composed of 6 experienced players (height: 170.9 ± 3.4 cm, weight: 66.6 ± 9.9 kg, experience period: 1.8 ± 1.1 years) and 6 beginners (height: 170.0 ± 2.1 cm, weight: 62.8 ± 7.2 kg). They performed a maximal instep kick by using crutches instead of the support leg. The peak vertical components of GRF (vGRF; superior: +) and anteroposterior components of GRF (apGRF; posterior: +) in the kicking leg side (KLS) and the non-kicking leg side (NKLS) generated by crutches were collected by eight force plates. In the experienced players, the peak vGRF of NKLS (8.2 ± 1.0 N/kg) was larger than that of KLS (7.1 ± 1.2 N/kg; $p < 0.05$), and the peak apGRF of NKLS (2.7 ± 0.5 N/kg) was larger than that of KLS (1.0 ± 0.4 N/kg; $p < 0.05$). In the beginners, the peak vGRF of NKLS (6.7 ± 1.3 N/kg) was larger than that of KLS (5.0 ± 1.8 N/kg; $p < 0.05$), and the peak apGRF of NKLS (1.3 ± 0.6 N/kg) was larger than that of KLS (0.7 ± 0.3 N/kg; $p < 0.05$). The GRF of experienced players in terms of all analyzed items were greater than those of beginners ($p < 0.05$). In amputee football, two crutches replace the support leg, particularly the crutch in NKLS which is the same side of support leg is required similar roles. Because amputee football players also approached the ball from an angle to the direction of ball flight, the vGRF and apGRF were larger in NKLS in both groups. Additionally, vGRF and apGRF of experienced players were greater than those of beginners. In conclusion, generating larger vGRF and apGRF, especially in NKLS, is important to improve the skills of instep kick in amputee football.

Keywords ground reaction force, amputee football, forearm crutch, Lofstrand crutch

Introduction

Amputee football is a sport designed for lower or upper extremity amputees. Recently, this sport has become increasingly popular worldwide because expensive specialized sporting equipment is unnecessary. A one-side lower extremity amputee plays as a field player using paired forearm

crutches, without wearing their prosthesis. In general football, it has been reported that the support leg plays an important role in improving kicking skill (Inoue, Nunome et al. 2014), and there are differences in the ground reaction forces (GRF) of experienced players and beginners (Nakamura, Saito et al. 2010). Therefore, the GRF of the crutch, which corresponds to the support leg in general football, is important to consider in improving kicking skill in amputee football. However, the GRF incurred by the crutch have not been clarified. Thus, the purpose of this study was to evaluate the GRF generated by the forearm crutches of amputee football players during the instep kick and to compare these values between experienced players and beginners. These findings will aid in improving kicking skill in amputee football.

Methods

Participants

Twelve collegiate students who have played general football for more than 5 years without amputation of their leg participated in this study as simulated amputees. Participants included 6 experienced players (height: 170.9 ± 3.4 cm, weight: 66.6 ± 9.9 kg, experience: 1.8 ± 1.1 years) and 6 beginners (height: 170.0 ± 2.1 cm, weight: 62.8 ± 7.2 kg). Experienced players were defined as those who had more than 6 months of experience playing amputee football.

Process

Participants performed the instep kick on force plates (AMTI Co., Ltd.) by using paired forearm crutches instead of their support leg. During the evaluation, participants were instructed to prevent their non-dominant leg from touching the floor. The kicking leg was designated as the dominant leg (Figure 1). The peak vertical components (vGRF; superior: +), anteroposterior components (apGRF; posterior: +), and mediolateral components of GRF (mIGRF; kicking leg side (KLS): +) in the KLS and the non-KLS (NKLS) generated by crutches were measured by the force plates at 1,000 Hz. To determine the analysis interval, the joint angle data was also measured using the VICON motion analysis system (Vicon Motion Analysis Systems Co., Ltd.).

Statistical analyses

The analysis interval was set to begin when one of crutches contacted the force plate and end at ball impact. A paired t-test was used to compare the GRF of the KLS and the NKLS. A non-paired t-test was used to compare the experienced group and beginner group. P values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Figure 1. Method for measuring GRF

Results

In the experienced group, the peak vGRF of the NKLS was greater than that of the KLS ($p < 0.05$), and the peak apGRF of the NKLS was greater than that of the KLS ($p < 0.05$). In the beginners, the peak vGRF of the NKLS was greater than that of the KLS ($p < 0.05$), and the peak apGRF of the NKLS was greater than that of the KLS ($p < 0.05$). For both sides, the vGRF and apGRF were greater in experienced players than in beginners ($p < 0.05$). The mIGRF were generated toward the medial direction, and that of the KLS was greater than that of the NKLS in both groups ($p < 0.05$). There were no significant differences between the experienced and beginner groups (Table 1). The direction in which the composite GRF of the three components occurred roughly coincided with the long axis direction of the crutch. In the experienced group, the composite GRF of the NKLS peaked near the maximum extension of the hip of the kicking leg (Figure 2).

Table 1. Maximum value of each ground reaction force component

	vGRF (superior: +)		apGRF (posterior: +)		mIGRF (KLS: +)	
	NKLS	KLS	NKLS	KLS	NKLS	KLS
Experienced	8.2 ± 1.0*†	7.1 ± 1.2*	2.7 ± 0.5*†	1.0 ± 0.4*	0.9 ± 0.7†	-2.4 ± 0.7*
Beginners	6.7 ± 1.3†	5.0 ± 1.2	1.3 ± 0.6†	0.7 ± 0.3	1.0 ± 0.4†	-1.5 ± 0.4

Mean ± SD (N/kg), *: $p < 0.05$ (vs. Beginners), †: $p < 0.05$ (vs. KLS)

Figure 2. Changes in composite GRF of the KLS and the NKLS during instep kick performance

Conclusion and discussion

In amputee football, two crutches replace the support leg, particularly the crutch of the NKLS, which is similar to the support leg required in similar roles. The vGRF and apGRF were greater in the NKLS in order to control movement in the fore-and-aft direction and to support the body weight, and mIGRF was greater in the KLS to prevent the body from falling in the direction of the KLS in both groups. This is because amputee football players also approached the ball from an angle, in relation to the direction of ball flight. Additionally, the vGRF and apGRF of experienced players were greater than those of beginners. The apGRF is a static frictional force. In order to kick while preventing the crutch from slipping, it is necessary to increase vGRF in the relationship between the static frictional force and the vGRF. Therefore, vGRF and apGRF are considered to be higher in the experienced group. In conclusion, generating greater vGRF and apGRF, especially in the NKLS, is important in improving instep kicking skills in amputee football.

References

Inoue K, Nunome H, Sterzing T, Shinkai H, Ikegami Y (2014) Dynamics of the support leg in soccer instep kicking. *J Sports Sci.* 32(11):1023-1032

Nakamura Y, Saito M, Hayashi T, Ehara Y (2010) Comparative Analysis of Instep Kicking Motion between Skilled Players and Beginners. *Biomechanism.* 20:53-64